

INFLUENCE OF ORGANIZATIONAL PRACTICES ON EMPLOYEE WELL-BEING

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Abstract

The well-being of employees in the workplace is an important issue. Employee well-being should occupy a very important place in institutional research. The research attempts to understand the influence of influence of organizational practices on employee well-being. Simple random sampling technique was used for primary data collection. Data was collected from 50 BHEL employees from Trichy. Data analysis was done through path analysis. The research concluded that there is influence of organizational practices such as workplace polices and rewards and recognition on employee well-being. The analysis also found that there is of employee well-being on employee job performance in BHEL, Trichy. BHEL management should provide a working environment such open communication policy, participation in management decision, and implement shorten feedback to employees. This will increase the well-being of the employees.

Keywords: Organizational Practices, Workplace Polices Rewards and Recognition, Employee Well-Being, And Employee Job Performance.

INTRODUCTION

The importance of organizational practices helps to maintain the well-being of employees. Furthermore, long-term organizational practices help business grow (Perrini & Tencati, 2006). Currently, the corporate world is undergoing a change due to globalization. Pfeffer (2010) stated that organizational and workplace polices can have far more harmful and far-reaching impacts than the effects on the world of employees and the social environment. Many workplace practices have adverse effects on employee health issues. Therefore, the management system of companies should be aware of the working practices of the employees. This study is designed to examine workplace policies and standardized organizational practices related to rewards and recognition. The primary aim of this study is to investigate the influence of organizational practices on employee well-being in BHEL, Trichy.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Organizational Practices and Employee Well-Being

Eshal Patil (2020) focused on the effects of specific HR practices on employee well-being. The research found the positive and strong effect was found between certain human resource management practices and employee well-being.

Guest (2017) examined the human resource management and employee well-being. The research found the positive and strong effect was found between certain human resource management practices and employee well-being.

Wong Foong Yee, Jo Ann Ho and Aziany Riziana Azahari (2016) found the job control (organizational practices) was the most dominant practice influencing employees' well-being. The research also found the employees' well-being was seen to be negatively related to turnover intention.

Vanhala and Tuomi (2006) tried to find out the relationship between well-being and the HR practices. The research found the relationship between HR practices and well-being, but it was seen as a good predictor of performance. Hence, the author frames the following hypotheses:

Ha1: Organizational practices predict employee well-being.

Employee Well-Being and Employee Job Performance

Yasir Mansoor Kundi, et al. (2021) found that there is a mediating effect of affective commitment between psychological well-being such as hedonic well-being and eudaimonic well-being with employee job performance.

Tzai-Chiao Lee, et al. (2021) found the Taiwanese sample had more significant development paths compared to mainland China employees in terms of employee employability, perceived organizational support, prior knowledge, self-efficacy, subjective wellbeing, and job performance.

Maziana Zakaria, Nik Kamaruzaman Abdulatiff, and Norli Ali (2014) investigated the effects of wellbeing on performance. Survey was done from 166 employees in services sector. The research indicated that there is a positive and significant relationship between wellbeing and performance. Hence, the author frames the following hypotheses:

Ha2: Employee well-being predicts employee job performance.

Organizational Practices and Employee Job Performance

Chumpon Rodjam, et al. (2020) revealed the effect of human resource management practices on employee performance. The research found the human resource management practices have significant and positive relationship with employee performance.

Tehmina Sattar, Khalil Ahmad and Syeda Mahnaz Hassan (2015) examined the impact of human resource (HR) practices on employees' performance. Data was from 181 employees of three leading banks of Multan city (Pakistan). The research found the HR practices (training, rewards and empowerment) were significantly related with employees' performance.

Shanthi Nadarajaha, et al. (2012) identified the association between job performance human resource practices. Outcomes of the research result could be useful to authorities in the improvement of HR practices as to ensure high successes of academic staffs' performance. Hence, the author frames the following hypotheses:

Ha3: Organizational practices predict employee job performance.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Descriptive research design has been used in this research work. The descriptive research design attempts to explain the activities of the employees in relation to an exacting practice or ethnicity of meaning. Based on the recompense of descriptive research design, the author has used the descriptive research to establish the influence of organizational practices on employee well-being in BHEL, Trichy.

Framework of the Research

It was used to identify the influence of organizational practices on employee well-being in BHEL. Organizational practices were considered as independent variables and classified into two groups such as workplace policies and rewards and recognition. Employee job performance was considered as outcome variable. Employee well-being was considered as mediator variable.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework of the study

Statement of the Problem

How organizational practices such as workplace policies and rewards and recognition influence the employee well-being and employee job performance. How the employee well-being influences the employee job performance in BHEL, Trichy.

Objectives of the Study

- To study the influence of organizational practices such as workplace policies and rewards and recognition on employee well-being.
- To know the influence of employee well-being on employee job performance in BHEL, Trichy.

Questionnaire Construction

Table 1: Reliability of the Research

S. No.	Variable	Reliability	Author
1	Organizational Practices		
	Workplace Polices	0.87	Rabindra Kumar Pradhan and Lopamudra Hati (2019)
	Rewards and Recognition	0.78	Manisha Gupta (2015)
2	Employee Well-Being	0.84	Lee, F.C.H.; Teh, P.-L.; Chan, A.H.S. (2021)
3	Employee Job Performance	0.89	Hira Aftab, Tayyaba Rana and Aamir Sarwar (2012)

Standard tools were used for primary data collection. For all the statements of the questionnaire construction the alpha was ranged from 0.78 to 89. This reliability value indicates that high reliability of the statements of the questionnaire.

Area of Sample and Justification

BHEL has been selected for this research as area of sampling. Hence, there is a required to defend and expand the employees as well as the BHEL as a whole. By understanding this, organizational practices, employee well-being, and employee job performance are judged for the research. The sample comprises the employees of BHEL, Trichy. Pilot study sample size of the research was 50 employees from BHEL, Trichy. Sampling technique presents a range of techniques that allow decreasing the amount of data wanted to collect by believing only data from a subgroup pretty than all probable cases or rudiments. Simple random sampling technique was followed to collect the primary data for the research.

Toll for Data Analysis

Path analysis was used for data analysis. It was used to identify the organizational practices such as workplace polices and rewards and recognition on employee job performance: the mediation effect of employee well-being in BHEL, Trichy.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2: Influence of employee psychological well-being on job performance

From the model fit table, it is identified that the chi-square value was 3.123. The p value was 0.135, which was greater than 5%. The GFI and AGFI scores were larger than 0.90, which was suggested by Saminathan, et al. (2019). The calculated CFI and NFI scores were larger than 0.90, which was suggested by and Kantiah Alias Deepak and Velaudham (2019); Velaudham and Baskar (2015). It was found that RMSEA and RMS values were less than 0.08. The above pointers indicate that it was completely fit Velaudham and Baskar (2016); Indra, Balaji and Velaudham (2020).

Table 2: shows Model Fit Indication

Indicators	Observed Values	Recommended Values (Premapriya, et al. 2016)
Chi-Square	3.123	---
p	0.135	< 0.050
GFI	0.997	> 0.90
AGFI	0.978	
CFI	0.999	
NFI	0.999	
RMS	0.018	> 0.080
RMSEA	0.002	

Source: Primary data

Table 3: Regression Weights

DV		IV	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	Beta	p
Employee Well-Being	<---	Workplace Polices	0.867	0.162	5.344	0.224	0.001
Employee Well-Being	<---	Rewards and Recognition	1.015	0.148	6.857	0.287	0.001
Employee Job Performance	<---	Workplace Polices	0.991	0.256	3.869	0.140	0.001
Employee Job Performance	<---	Rewards and Recognition	3.349	0.237	14.150	0.519	0.001
Employee Job Performance	<---	Employee Well-Being	0.636	0.057	11.078	0.348	0.001

Source: Primary data

H₀: There is no influence of workplace polices on employee well-being.

Influence of workplace polices on employee well-being calculated value of CR is 5.344. The Beta value was 0.224. The beta value indicates that 22.4 percent of influence is through workplace polices towards employee well-being. The p value was 0.001. The p value was less than 5% and the hypothesis was rejected. The result shows that the workplace polices influences employee well-being among the employees in BHEL. Eshal Patil (2020); Guest (2017); Wong Foong Yee, et al. (2016); and Vanhala and Tuomi (2006) have found similar result.

H₀: There is no influence of rewards and recognition on employee well-being.

Influence of rewards and recognition on employee well-being calculated value of CR is 6.857. The Beta value was 0.287. The beta value indicates that 28.7 percent of influence is through rewards and recognition towards employee well-being. The p value was 0.001. The p value was less than 5% and the hypothesis was rejected. The result shows that the rewards and

recognition influences employee well-being among the employees in BHEL. Eshal Patil (2020); Guest (2017); Wong Foong Yee, et al. (2016); and Vanhala and Tuomi (2006) have found similar result.

H₀: There is no influence of workplace polices on employee job performance.

Influence of workplace polices on employee job performance calculated value of CR is 3.869. The Beta value was 0.140. The beta value indicates that 14 percent of influence is through workplace polices towards employee job performance. The p value was 0.001. The p value was less than 5% and the hypothesis was rejected. The result shows that the workplace polices influences employee job performance among the employees in BHEL. Chumpon Rodjam, et al. (2020); Tehmina Sattar, Khalil Ahmad and Syeda Mahnaz Hassan (2015); and Shanthi Nadarajaha, et al. (2012) have found similar result.

H₀: There is no influence of rewards and recognition on employee job performance.

Influence of rewards and recognition on employee job performance calculated value of CR is 14.150. The Beta value was 0.519. The beta value indicates that 51.9 percent of influence is through rewards and recognition towards employee job performance. The p value was 0.001. The p value was less than 5% and the hypothesis was rejected. The result shows that the rewards and recognition influences employee job performance among the employees in BHEL. Chumpon Rodjam, et al. (2020); Tehmina Sattar, Khalil Ahmad and Syeda Mahnaz Hassan (2015); and Shanthi Nadarajaha, et al. (2012) have found similar result.

H₀: There is no influence of employee well-being on employee job performance.

Influence of employee well-being on employee job performance calculated value of CR is 11.078. The Beta value was 0.348. The beta value indicates that 34.8 percent of influence is through employee well-being towards employee job performance. The p value was 0.001. The p value was less than 5% and the hypothesis was rejected. The result shows that the employee well-being influences employee job performance among the employees in BHEL. Yasir Mansoor Kundi, et al. (2021); Tzai-Chiao Lee, et al. (2021); Maziana Zakaria, Nik Kamaruzaman Abdulatiff, and Norli Ali (2014) have found similar result.

FINDINGS

- The research found the workplace polices influences employee well-being among the employees in BHEL. Eshal Patil (2020); Guest (2017); Wong Foong Yee, et al. (2016); and Vanhala and Tuomi (2006) have found similar result.
- It is discovered the rewards and recognition influences employee well-being among the employees in BHEL. Eshal Patil (2020); Guest (2017); Wong Foong Yee, et al. (2016); and Vanhala and Tuomi (2006) have found similar result.
- The analysis identified the workplace polices influences employee job performance among the employees in BHEL. Chumpon Rodjam, et al. (2020); Tehmina Sattar, Khalil Ahmad and Syeda Mahnaz Hassan (2015); and Shanthi Nadarajaha, et al. (2012) have found similar result.

- From, the analysis it is found the rewards and recognition influences employee job performance among the employees in BHEL. Chumpon Rodjam, et al. (2020); Tehmina Sattar, Khalil Ahmad and Syeda Mahnaz Hassan (2015); and Shanthi Nadarajaha, et al. (2012) have found similar result.
- The result shows that the employee well-being influences employee job performance among the employees in BHEL. Yasir Mansoor Kundi, et al. (2021); Tzai-Chiao Lee, et al. (2021); Maziana Zakaria, Nik Kamaruzaman Abdulatiff, and Norli Ali (2014) have found similar result.

Suggestions

- BHEL management should provide a working environment such open communication policy, participation in management decision, and implement shorten feedback to employees. This will increase the well-being of the employees.
- Authorities of BHEL should provide recognitions & rewards of compensation practices such as extrinsic rewards, rewards related to performance, intrinsic rewards, fairness in recognition and rewards, and reward for overtime or any other extra work to their employees.

CONCLUSION

The well-being of employees in the workplace is an important issue. Employee well-being should occupy a very important place in institutional research. The research attempts to understand the influence of influence of organizational practices on employee well-being. Simple random sampling technique was used for primary data collection. Data was collected from 50 BHEL employees from Trichy. Data analysis was done through path analysis. The research concluded that there is influence of organizational practices such as workplace polices and rewards and recognition on employee well-being. The analysis also found that there is of employee well-being on employee job performance in BHEL, Trichy. BHEL management should provide a working environment such open communication policy, participation in management decision, and implement shorten feedback to employees. This will increase the well-being of the employees.

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